

IMPORTANCE OF OBTAINING GLOBAL GAP CERTIFICATES FOR AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS INCLUDING CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES INCLUDING UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract. *All over the world, there is a lot of practical work on food safety. Every Agrarian country wants to export its produce and get good profit from it. But world markets have their own standard requirements and specified certificates. One such certification is the Global G.A.P standards. Below you will get a better understanding of Global G.A.P standards and Global G.A.P benefits in exporting products in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *global G.A.P., standard, Global G.A.P benefits, Uzbekistan, export, Certification, agricultural, products.*

Introduction

Today the main engine of the GlobalG.A.P. Standard. - retail chains, processing plants and catering establishments. Guaranteeing the safety of products offered to consumers is one of the main requirements. For example, a key condition for purchased products from the vast majority of European supermarkets is compliance with the requirements of GlobalG.A.P.. Achieving GLOBALG.A.P. certification delivers multiple advantages, including:

- Enhanced food safety management systems for your farm
- Demonstrates your commitment to producing and trading safe food
- Acceptance into the GLOBALG.A.P. community
- Increased consumer and customer confidence in your product's safety and quality.

Aim

- To study the current situation of export of agricultural products in Uzbekistan.
- To study how the implementation of Global G.A.P is progressing in Uzbekistan.
- Is Global G.A.P affecting export performance
- Learning how to change exports if we introduce Global G.A.P Farm Certification

Materials and methods

During the research, the number of farms growing agricultural products based on the requirements of international food standards in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, annual statistics of export products collected from agroclusters and other agricultural enterprises were used. The analysis was performed by statistical comparison of the collected data.

Year-on-year growth of companies around the world with Global G.A.P certification

Results

As a result of the conducted research and analysis, the following results were achieved:

- GlobalG.A.P. Uzbekistan is undergoing major changes in the field of export of agricultural products. Including, today more than 60 enterprises GlobalG.A.P. has received a certificate and is easily exporting its products to European countries. In the period from 2019 to 2022, 50-70% of fresh fruits, 10-15% of processed products, 10-15% of dried products and spices, canned products made up the rest.

- We are conducting our research in cooperation with "Uzstandart" agency. "Uzstandart" agency provides practical assistance to enterprises producing local export products in connection with the introduction of international standards.

- To date, 65 enterprises in our country have received the GLOBAL GAP certificate, and "AGRO LIGHT BUSINESS" and "Ezgulik Sari Agro" farms in Qibray district of Tashkent region were awarded by "Uzstandart" agency in order to support local farms and producers during the COVID 19 pandemic. practical assistance was provided to export their products. These enterprises were awarded certificates based on the international GLOBAL GAP standard. This event was organized in cooperation with metrology and certification departments of Chirchik. Enterprises certified on the basis of this international standard were given the opportunity to export their farm products to European markets. Also, certification processes based on the GLOBAL GAP standard are currently being implemented in the enterprises of "Madina Khang Agro" LLC and "Lead agriculture development" LLC JV in Tashkent region.

Based on the above, the GLOBAL GAP certificate will greatly help the producers of our Republic in the import of products. Year by year, the demand for this certificate in our republic is increasing.

Conclusion

1. GLOBALG.A.P. certification is necessary for the export of food products of good quality and for selling them at a higher price
2. By digitizing agriculture and using new technologies, less human labor is used

3. Global G.A.P. if we use the certificate, we can attract more foreign customers if we prepare our products for export.

4. So, our republic is cultivated in agriculture in order for their products to take a strong place in the international markets, it is appropriate to certify agricultural producers according to the Global G.A.P system.

REFERENCES

1. Republic of Uzbekistan - Certification of products and services Law on
2. Abduvaliev A.A., Latipov V.B., Umarov A.S., Alimov M.N., et al. "Standardization,
3. Metrology, Certification, Quality.» - T.: SMSITI, 2008. - 267 p.